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STUDII

SOCIOLOGIE ȘI ANTROPOLOGIE

INSIDE THE COLLECTIVE PSYCHE. FROM METAPHYSICAL SPECTRE TO C. RĂDULESCU-MOTRU'S PSYCHOLOGY OF THE ROMANIAN PEOPLE

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Abstract. *This article intends to serve as a brief excursus into the evolution of the pioneering study of the human mind in the modern era, examining the intricate components of its inner workings, its nature as both a psychological and physiological phenomenon, and, more importantly, its outward social and cultural dimensions. Thematically, it is structured along two parts: the first provides a historical narrative that traces the journey from the English philosopher Thomas Hobbes to the German physiologist and experimental psychologist Wilhelm Wundt, emphasizing the challenges of pushing past the confines of theoretical metaphysics and establishing proper empirical foundations for the then emerging sciences of psychology and sociology; the second part transitions into an applied analysis, focusing on Romanian philosopher and psychologist Constantin Rădulescu-Motru's attempts to draw a distinct psychological portrait of the Romanian people.*

Keywords: *Mind-Body Dualism, Physicalism, Social Psychology, Cultural Selection Theory, Völkerpsychologie.*

APRÈS LA MÉTAPHYSIQUE

Setting aside the contributions of the Oriental thinkers of the Islamic Golden Age – who experienced a remarkable intellectual renaissance emerging out of Classical Antiquity; particularly through their role in the preservation and advancement of Aristotelian thought, and whose achievements remain largely unacknowledged within the European tradition due to entrenched linguistic, cultural, and, above all, religious prejudices that have obstructed the recognition of their essential role in reshaping the directions of philosophy towards what we may call a more scientific approach and the incorporation of their innovations within the Western canon – the first major body of work in Europe to thoroughly and exhaustively address social, and by extension political, issues is the collection of treatises by the English philosopher Thomas

Hobbes. *De Cive* [*On the Citizen*], published in 1647, explores the general principles of natural laws, government, and religion. It lay the groundwork for Hobbes's ideas on the social contract, civil governance, and the role of authority in maintaining peace and order in any given community. *De Corpore* [*On the Body*], published in 1655, despite its title, delves into logic, mathematics, and scientific concepts, focusing on Hobbes's method of reasoning and the foundations of knowledge. *De Homine* [*On Man*], published in 1658, shifts the focus to human nature and the political and social concerns of the time, exploring the mechanisms of perception, the nature of the will, and how these influence political life. Though not published in their originally intended order, with *De Cive* actually conceived as the conclusion, they collectively constitute the *Elementorum Philosophiae*, more commonly referred to in English as *The Elements of Philosophy*. Together, they form a foundational corpus in Hobbes's thought, presenting his views on everything from the nature of knowledge and science to the mechanics of human behaviour and the governance of societies. The addition of *Leviathan* in 1651 served to further his political theories, offering a more comprehensive view of the social contract and stressing the need for a sovereign authority. *Behemoth*, posthumously published in 1681, complements this body by providing a historical and political commentary on the English Civil War. These works constitute an in-depth exploration of political philosophy, combining natural philosophy, human psychology, and political theory into a coherent system.

In a letter dedicated to his younger patron, William Cavendish, the 3rd Earl of Devonshire, Hobbes informs him of his intentions to supersede what he considered "pernicious philosophy" (Hobbes, 1655/1839, p. x) and to "frighten away and drive out this metaphysical Empusa" (Hobbes, 1655/1839, p. xi). An Empusa being a shape-shifting spectre or entity in Greek mythology, often depicted as a female figure with vampiric or cannibalistic inclinations. She was typically a servant of the goddess Hecate and would transform her appearance to seduce and prey upon unsuspecting young men. The figure of the Empusa served as a cautionary personification of the dangers of seduction and deception, representing not just physical danger but also moral corruption. This character, as invoked by Hobbes, signifies the confusion he aimed to "exorcize" from natural philosophy, symbolically casting out the falsehoods and delusions that clouded human understanding and impeded rational inquiry, that is, the hitherto metaphysical direction in natural philosophy, which he considered tainted by superstition and false divinity. His aim was to meticulously separate the rules of religion from the rules of philosophy, advocating for a natural philosophy grounded in reason and empirical evidence, free from the influence of any doctrine or dogma, be it Christian or pagan.

Influenced by his contemporary Francis Bacon – whom we know he was close to, having served as Bacon's personal assistant and amanuensis,

transcribing much of his works – Hobbes championed the importance of natural philosophy. He found in Bacon the answer to what this new foundation could and should in fact be – namely, science. Guided by the “Baconian method” and Bacon’s approach to causality, Hobbes sought to apply a rigorous, empirical method to the study of politics and human nature. He identified two primary areas of interest in philosophy, both concerned with different kinds of bodies. The first was the *natural body*, composed of the biological organisms of individuals, while the second was the *body politic*, or the *commonwealth*, formed through the wills, and agreements, of said individuals. From this distinction, Hobbes derived two branches of philosophy: one *natural* and one *civil*. However, in order to fully understand the nature of the commonwealth, he believed it was essential to first unravel the complexities of its social mechanisms, and for this one must first analyse their main actors, the individual human persons, as they are the foundational components whose interactions and behaviours shape the collective structure of society. This new *civil philosophy* that he envisioned was in turn divided into two further parts: the study of the dispositions, affections, and manners of individuals, which he referred to as *ethics*, and the study of their civil duties, which he called *politics* (Hobbes, 1656/1839, p. 11). By this he sought to explain how the natural tendencies of individuals influence the functioning and governance of society, with both ethical and political dimensions essential for a just civil order. Thus, he established a binomial pair from part to whole that was integral to the relation between the “movements of the mind” and his civil philosophy, focusing specifically on how these mental motions can be harnessed for a fair governance, emphasizing the importance of understanding the human mind, based on scientific knowledge and reason, as a prerequisite for any effective political theory and practice (Hobbes, 1656/1839, pp. 73f).

Having lived through the turbulences of both the Thirty Years’ War and the British Civil Wars, Hobbes developed a pronounced aversion to hierarchical churches, whose involvement in political machinations he blamed for causing these catastrophes. He viewed the entanglement of religion and politics as a source of division and chaos, leading him to advocate for the subordination of religious authority to civil authority in order to prevent the destructive influence of clerical power over political stability. Thus, he deemed necessary for a civil philosophy to be distinct from theology. This separation of ethics from any ecclesiastical interference was crucial, as it allowed civil philosophy to function alongside natural philosophy, and to focus on practical, scientific inquiry into human nature and the tools of governance without being tangled by religious canons (Hobbes, 1655/1839, p. xi).

The boundaries between psychology, sociology, and philosophy at the time were still fluid, with many thinkers addressing questions about human behaviour, society, and the mind within a philosophical framework. Today, these topics

would be categorized under psychology, but at the time, they were considered part of the philosophy of mind, as they dealt mainly with mental processes. Hobbes also laid the foundations of a new type of philosophy that now would fall under the auspices of sociology, illustrating how the interplay between individual mental states and social contexts was recognized even in such an early discourse on what could be considered modern social issues. His writings continued to exert significant influence throughout the Scientific Revolution, determining the course of political theory and scientific inquiry alike. So profound was his impact that there is hardly any contemporary discipline that has escaped untouched by this Hobbesian inheritance. The American political philosopher Karl Widerquist and anthropologist Grant McCall commenting on the importance of Hobbes in anthropology, stated that: “Hobbesian ideas were not merely influential in anthropology; they were foundational. The history of anthropology is largely a history of how these ideas were overcome, but Hobbesian viewpoints of some kind have never entirely gone away” (Widerquist, K., and McCall G.S., 2017, p. 112). One of these points they dub “the Hobbesian hypothesis”. In its most basic form, it argues that individuals are better off, or at least not worse, under an authority, implicitly that of a corporation, such as the state, than they might reasonably be expected to be in a society devoid of it, as the existence of such an authority provides a level of order and security that life outside it simply cannot guarantee (Widerquist, K., and McCall G.S., 2017, p. 4).

The investigation of the psychological aspects, rather than the purely epistemic ones in the philosophy of mind began along two distinct traditions: the first is that of British philosophy represented by Thomas Hobbes himself, John Locke, and David Hume; the second is the Continental one represented by René Descartes, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, and Christian Wolff. Ultimately, they will both converge and find a melting point – a radical synthesis – in the philosophy of Immanuel Kant. The Lockean supposition of a *tabula rasa* in turn tells us that even if focused on the individual mind, psychology cannot uncover its determinations solely within the mind itself. Rather, these determinations emerge from an intricate web of interactions, whether biological – physical and chemical, or social – both at an interpersonal level between individuals and at an impersonal level through engagement with society and culture. It is only in this broader relational context that the mind is able to conceptualize its structure and meaning. This set the course for philosophy to move beyond metaphysics, charting a new path that prioritized empirical investigation and scientific reasoning by rejecting the speculative elements that had dominated earlier traditions. This shift not only sought to eliminate the obscurity and ambiguity associated with metaphysical doctrines but also aimed to align philosophy more closely with the methods and rigors of the budding natural sciences, steering it toward a more grounded, systematic exploration of knowledge.

THE MIND AS PART OF NATURE. TOWARDS A SCIENCE OF THE PSYCHE

The relationship between *psyche* the soul and *psyche* the mind had been a close and intricate one throughout history, often intertwined and disputed within various philosophical, theological, and scientific traditions. However, the modern conception of the mind marks a significant departure from earlier metaphysical and religious interpretations. The mind was no longer seen as an isolated, immaterial entity distinct from the body or the world, but rather as integrated into, and interacting with, the natural order. This reflected a broader transition from viewing the soul as a supernatural essence or divine principle to understanding the mind as a natural phenomenon, and to discover the laws governing these mental phenomena – perception, thought, emotion, and behaviour.

Although still deeply rooted in the metaphysical tradition, German philosopher Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz in his 1714 *La Monadologie* [*Monadology*] summarized a dualistic principle where souls and bodies are governed by fundamentally different principles. For him, souls functioned according to the laws of final causes through *appetitions*, ends, and means based on internal desires and purposes. In contrast, bodies operated according to the laws of efficient causes – mechanical laws of motion that were governed by external forces and interactions (1714/2014, §79). However, he postulated that these two separate realms – mental and physical – were not in chaotic disjunction but instead existed in a state of perfect consonance with one another by virtue of a concept he termed the *doctrine of pre-established harmony* (Leibniz, 1714/2014, §78). According to which, while the mind and body did not interact causally, God, in his infinite wisdom, had made them to coordinate perfectly in such a way so that both operate *as if* they were in a relation of causal interaction. To every mental state corresponded a physical state and vice versa, but they did so independently, like two perfectly synchronized clocks set in motion by a celestial hand. This divine arrangement, Leibniz argued, ensured that the mental and physical realms were in complete harmony without requiring any direct communication or causal influence between them (Leibniz, 1714/2014, §81). In other words, although the mind and body followed their respective laws, they unfolded in perfect parallelism. Needless to say, this system was met with significant opposition and would go on to be fiercely challenged by later thinkers. Leibniz seemed to bypass the problem of causal interaction by resorting to a theological explanation, effectively leaving unresolved the deeper question of how two such disparate substances could be so intricately linked. This led to further developments both in metaphysics and the philosophy of mind in order to do away with Leibniz's harmonization and provide a more naturalistic account of the relationship between mind and body.

What Leibniz established was a problem that was to be constantly debated even up to the German physiologist and experimental psychologist Wilhelm Wundt

(1874/1903, p. 771). This “metaphysical parallelism” Wundt will eventually term *psychophysical parallelism* (Wundt, 1874/1903, pp. 768ff). However, he argued that instead of invoking the ultimate God substance, the “miracle” explanation should be examined in such a way that the miracle itself disappears, rendering it a reasonable, even logically inevitable necessity (Wundt, 1874/1903, p. 771). He did not consider the principle of psychophysical parallelism to be a metaphysical principle (Wundt, 1874/1903, p. 770), but a heuristic one, which served as a methodological tool to preserve the perspectives that allows the two complementary scientific points of view – the purely objective one of the natural sciences and the subjective one of psychology – to be combined without contradiction. And, since neither of the two can claim to capture the whole of reality on its own, the heuristic principle of psychophysical parallelism cannot be more than a maxim, indispensable as long as it is a matter of uniting the results of natural empirical research on the one hand and empirical psychology on the other (Wundt, 1874/1903, pp. 773f), but refutable otherwise. Later on, Romanian philosopher and psychologist Constantin Rădulescu-Motru’s solution to this parallelism would reside within a monism with which he intended to lay the foundations of his own novel science of the soul – *energetic personalism* (See Lupașcu, 2023).

In his *Metaphysische Anfangsgründe der Naturwissenschaft* [Metaphysical Foundations of Natural Science], published in 1786 between the first edition of his *Kritik der reinen Vernunft* [Critique of Pure Reason] in 1781 and its second edition in 1787, Immanuel Kant acknowledged, as with Descartes before him, that philosophy admitted a dual doctrine of nature: the doctrine of the body and the doctrine of the soul. In this framework, the former understood the body as *res extensa* – an “extended thing” that occupied a specific place in space, while the latter understood the soul as *res cogitans* – a “thinking and non-extended thing”. From here, any comprehensive doctrine that aspires to be a system, that is, a body of knowledge organized according to principles, could be called a science. Since these principles may be either empirical or rational, natural science – whether concerning the body or the soul – would have to be classified as either historical or rational natural science. The latter requiring a reasoned understanding of the interconnections of natural phenomena, to the extent that such understanding qualified as scientific. Thus, the doctrine of nature could be more precisely divided into first the historical doctrine of nature, which contained systematically ordered facts about natural things – this in turn consisting of natural description, a system for classifying natural things based on their similarities, and natural history, a methodical account of natural things across time and space – then second into natural science – which itself could be divided into proper and improper sciences. The former dealing with its objects purely through a priori principles, while the latter relied on the laws of experience, and therefore on a posteriori principles (Kant, 1786/2004, pp. 3f).

The distinction between *a priori* and *a posteriori* knowledge referred to what preceded or followed from what, if not the mind itself? These categories inherently presuppose the mind as the centre point from which knowledge could be either independent of experience – *a priori*, or derived from it – *a posteriori*. Thus, a deadlock occurs in the Kantian explanation of phenomena regarding the complexity resultant of any attempt at reconciling the *noumenal* and *phenomenal* realms, and the place of the human consciousness in-between them, thereby exposing the limits of human knowledge which could not be overcome by reason alone. Although Kant himself stated in his second preface to his *Critique of Pure Reason* that he established these limits leaving suffice “[...] room for faith; and the dogmatism of metaphysics [...]” (Kant, 1787/2009, p. 117), he asserted that the empirical doctrine of the soul remained farther still from plausible because mathematics was not applicable to the phenomena of inner senses and the laws governing them. Consequently, the empirical study of the soul could never advance beyond being a historical doctrine of nature, as such serving only as a natural description of the soul, but never a science of the soul (Kant, 1786/2004, p. 7).

With this Kant denied fellow German philosopher Christian Wolff’s project of establishing a scientific psychology. Wolff’s most significant contribution to psychology had been his clear distinction between two methods of investigating the soul: *empirical psychology*, based on the observation of one’s own mind, and *rational psychology*, which sought to uncover truths about the soul using reason, independent of experience (Mamulea, 2021, p. 149). Kant, who regarded Wolff as the greatest of the dogmatic philosophers, rejected both the possibility of rational psychology and empirical psychology. In regards to the former, Kant argued that reason alone, with its abstract concepts and logical instruments, lacked the capacity to yield any genuine knowledge of the soul. He critiqued the dogmatic assumptions of rational psychology, especially its attempts to deduce the nature of the soul purely through insight, dismissing such efforts as speculative and unfounded. As for the latter, he contended that such an endeavour was impossible as well, since psychological phenomena, being strictly subjective, could not be expressed mathematically. Whereas natural sciences relied on both time and space to quantify and measure phenomena, Kant argued that mental processes existed only in the dimension of time and lacked the spatial qualities necessary for mathematical representation. Moreover, he maintained that because these psychical phenomena were strictly subjective and tied to individual experience, they could not be tested in experimental conditions, as they were intimately tied to the individual in question and thus fell outside the realm of objective scientific inquiry (Mamulea, 2021, p. 149).

As the conviction that the mind was a part of nature became more prevalent in the 19th century, it gave rise to an ever increasing need to explain it by causal references to natural phenomena and laws. If the mind was a product of nature, then it must be subject to the same fundamental set of laws that governed all

natural phenomena (Mamulea, 2021, p. 152). On the other hand, the constitution of this new object of study implied the sacrifice of subjectivity, because qualities, as they were experienced in the first person, as Kant claimed, could not be the object of quantitative research (Mamulea, 2021, p. 147). There also remained the unresolved question of how the transition from matter in motion, reducible to atoms and their inherent forces, to the qualities of consciousness actually took place (Mamulea, 2021, p. 148). And thus, the manner in which the materialist perspective of physical processes with the metaphysical experiential, often intangible, qualities that constituted perceptions and conscious thought could be reconciled. Therefore, not long after, German philosopher Johann Friedrich Herbart, the direct successor to Kant's professorship at the University of Königsberg, sought to address these issues in 1816 with his *Lehrbuch zur Psychologie* [*Textbook in Psychology*]. Against Kant's predictions, he introduced the quantitative study of the mind by demonstrating that psychic phenomena do indeed unfold along two dimensions: time and intensity, while also making the first attempts to mathematize these processes in what would be known as *mathematical psychology* (Mamulea, 2021, p. 149). His contributions did not stop here as in his 1824 *Psychologie Als Wissenschaft* [*Psychology as Science*] he also sought to establish a new system analogous to physics to investigate psychic faculties by extending natural causality to mental phenomena, thereby seeking to bridge the gap between the physical and the psychological (Mamulea, 2021, p. 150).

Just as empirical physics, though not yet having discovered the fundamental forces of nature, had nevertheless identified certain laws governing phenomena through experiments with artificial tools and the application of mathematics, psychology had to similarly strive for this scientific accuracy. Like the natural sciences, it had to assume that all phenomena, without exception, were governed by a set of laws. Wherever possible, these laws should be measured and expressed through mathematical calculations. While psychology could not (yet) experiment on human beings the same way that the empirical sciences did, nor did it have the tools for this purpose, mathematics became all the more vital in ensuring the precision needed in establishing its foundational principles. From there, the process of relating individual cases to general laws could begin (Herbart, 1816/1894, p. 4). Here Herbart praised Locke and Leibniz with advancing along a better path in psychology than Wolff and Kant, who came after them (Herbart, 1816/1894, p. 7).

Constantin Rădulescu-Motru credits Herbart with having managed to separate the soul into its fundamental elements, which he identified as representations – *Vorstellung*, and with constructing a “mechanics” of these representations – *Vorstellungsmechanik*, treating them as forces that interact with each other according to specific laws yet to be determined (Rădulescu-Motru, 1912, p. 26). This mechanistic framework allowed for a quantitative analysis of mental processes. A first crucial step towards moving psychology away from metaphysical speculation and towards a more systematic, scientific investigation of

the mind. Although on the same occasion Motru expressed his disappointment and lamented that this approach lacked continuators who could further develop and complete Herbart's method, with that many psychological phenomena remaining unaccounted for.

Thus, according to the new psychology, consciousness was no longer seen only as a passive spectator to the acts of the soul, as it had been generally considered before. Instead, it was understood as the totality of said acts. Motru argued that *a consciousness does not exist independently of the acts that constitute it*. It was not a reflexive mirror, a separate entity observing the workings of the mind, but the very sum of its mental activities and processes (Rădulescu-Motru, 1912, p. 64). With this perspective, an attempt was made to challenge the earlier dualistic conception of a detached, observing self – which had long been viewed as unable to interact directly with the physical components of the mind and body – thereby breaking down the rigid boundary between the two realms. The integrated understanding of human experience, where mental and physical processes were viewed as interdependent and inseparable, real progress in establishing psychology as a science could now be made. This shift allowed researchers to systematically investigate cognitive processes, behaviours, and their physiological correlates, providing psychology with the methodical rigor needed to emerge as an independent discipline.

The next relevant figure in our study is the German physiologist Emil Du Bois-Reymond. A student of another prominent German, Johannes Peter Müller, a professor of anatomy and physiology, Du Bois-Reymond initially found himself influenced by Müller's commitment to vitalism. At the time, vitalist biology held that living organisms possessed some privileged property, substance, or even a metaphysical soul, which distinguished them fundamentally from non-living entities. Du Bois-Reymond's academic trajectory took a decisive turn when Müller asked him to investigate into the works of Italian neurophysiologist Carlo Matteucci, a pioneer in the study of *bioelectricity* – the electrical phenomena exhibited by living beings. Matteucci had recently completed a series of groundbreaking experiments refining his fellow Italian physician and physicist Luigi Galvani's "frog's galvanoscope" – an instrument comprised of a skinned frog's leg, which had its nerves connected to an electric source, such as a voltaic pile, whose discharges could be used to observe muscular contractions. Matteucci used this technique to explore the association between electricity and muscle functions, including that of human muscles. The purpose of these experiments was to disprove the theory of vitalism by demonstrating that living organisms were not fundamentally distinct from non-living entities but, rather, shared many basic properties. Building on this foundation, Du Bois-Reymond conducted further experiments and established that nerves and muscles could generate measurable electrical currents. He argued that the phenomena previously thought to be the clearest manifestations of vital forces – such as nerve and muscle activity – were,

in fact, entirely explicable in physical and chemical terms (Gaukroger, 2020, p. 173). This marked a turning point not only in the study of physiology but also in the broader philosophical debates about life and consciousness. By demonstrating bioelectricity as a fundamental characteristic of living tissues, Du Bois-Reymond challenged the core assumptions of vitalism and set the stage for a more mechanistic and scientifically grounded understanding of life processes.

But Du Bois-Reymond would become even more infamous for a controversy he sparked following his lecture at the 45th Assembly of German Naturalists and Physicians in Leipzig on 14 August 1872, later published with the title *Über die Grenzen des Naturerkennens* [*On the Limits of our Knowledge of Nature*]. Here he articulated his principle of *ignoramus et ignorabimus* – that we are ignorant and we shall remain ignorant (Mamulea, 2021, p. 152). He argued that there are inherent limitations to human knowledge – not surprisingly, as Herbart had already mathematically defined a *limen*, a boundary for consciousness – particularly regarding the ultimate nature of matter and the mind-body problem. With this reiterating a doctrine held by the ancient sceptic philosophers that human knowledge could never amount to certainty, but only to probability. Later on, at a session of the Royal Academy of Sciences in Berlin on 8 July 1880, on the occasion of Leibniz’s anniversary, Du Bois-Reymond would introduce another set of issues – the *Welträtsel* – “the seven riddles of the universe”: 1) the ultimate nature of matter and force; 2) the origin of motion; 3) the origin of life; 4) the apparently teleological arrangement of nature; 5) the origin of simple sensations; 6) the origin of intelligent thought and language; 7) and the question of free will (Veit-Brause, 2001, p. 42). These enigmas would once again be deemed unanswerable. With these two lectures he would significantly undermine the ambitions of metaphysics by casting doubt on its ability to address its own ultimate questions. This bold acataleptic claim suggested that certain answers, such as how physical processes gives rise to consciousness or what underlies the fundamental nature of matter, would remain eternally unattainable. From his part, this was not a form of temporary agnosticism that he mandated, but a permanent condition for human knowledge, placing certain philosophical and scientific inquiries forever beyond our reach. Thus, his lectures posited an insurmountable boundary for science, implying that the pursuit of these ultimate questions was futile. With this he incited a wave of reactions from both scientists and philosophers alike. Many saw it as a declaration of defeatism of the scientific method. A stark reversal of the prevailing optimism of the time, which held that science would eventually reveal all the secrets of nature.

In Romanian philosophy, this limitation would have strong echoes beginning from Titu Maiorescu to Constantin Rădulescu-Motru and Lucian Blaga. Motru offered a categorical response to Du Bois-Reymond’s sceptical stance regarding the limits of scientific knowledge: “From the relative ignorance of an epoch we

have no right to conclude that the solution is definitively impossible” (Rădulescu-Motru, 1897, p. 57). He remained very positive that what seemed intractable in one era could become intelligible in the future as scientific knowledge and methodologies continue to evolve. And indeed, he dedicated a considerable portion of his works to countering Du Bois-Reymond in particular, though not in person of course as the latter had already passed away in 1896. For Motru, the conscious act appears as a rupture of material uniformity. To be conscious meant to be connected to a self that stood in opposition to what did not belong to itself. Consciousness, in this sense, was the self’s reaction against nature. However, from a physiological perspective, neither the self nor the reactive acts of the self could be distinguished from the rest of the processes occurring within the human body (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929a, p. 306). Psychology, he claimed, can derive no benefit from the explanations provided by physiology as long as physiology remains grounded solely in pure mechanics (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929a, p. 306), as the mechanistic approach, focused exclusively on material processes and causality, failed to account for the complexities of consciousness and mental life, which demanded an entirely separate holistic and non-reducible framework for exploring the nature of psychological phenomena beyond physical interactions. Merely replacing one set of physical-chemical facts with another, even if they were more precise, still leaves us within the realm of physical bodies as long as these facts are governed by the same underlying laws, no matter how refined (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929a, pp. 305f). The biologist’s interest in the human mind must extend beyond just cataloguing the various compounds that constitute organic matter or examining their physical properties in isolation. Instead, the emphasis must fall on understanding the form and conditions under which these elements correlate and, once correlated, how they manifest as a coherent organic unit in interaction with its environment. The focus, therefore, must be directed on the functional unity that emerges, rather than the apparent aggregation of material components, revealing the integrated and purposeful organization of life (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929a, p. 307). He criticized Du Bois-Reymond and his followers for erring in their attempts to explain the complex biological functions of consciousness solely through the positioning and movement of individual material atoms taken independently of the organic unity in which they exist. He contended that this approach mistakenly conceived consciousness only as a mere reflection of uniform matter in motion, rather than recognizing it as a function of individuality (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929a, p. 307).

THE ADVENT OF POSITIVISM

The advent of the *positive method* represented a transformative shift in the history of human thought, marking a definitive departure from speculative metaphysics and abstract contemplation to a more empirical and scientifically

grounded approach. It is closely associated with the philosophy of *positivism* – from the French *positif*, ultimately derived from the Latin *positivus*, in its philosophical meaning “imposed on the mind by experience”, totally unrelated to the common understanding of happiness or optimism – and its strict emphasis on knowledge rooted in observable facts. Positivism as a doctrine was systematized by the French philosopher Auguste Comte in the early 19th century.

Comte had been a student at the *École Polytechnique*, a prestigious institution for science and engineering, founded in 1794 by the French mathematician Gaspard Monge during the French Revolution, and militarized in 1804 under Napoleon I, by this time becoming a military academy. This environment reinforced a commitment to discipline in the service to the state and steeped the young Comte in the revolutionary ideals of secularism and republicanism. As a result, his ideological convictions frequently put him at odds with his Catholic and monarchist family, causing bitter tensions between the modernity of his education and the entrenched traditionalism of his upbringing. This friction would become increasingly pronounced in the later stages of his intellectual career. The Polytechnique was due to be reformed during the Bourbon Restoration, and so Comte left without applying for reenrolment. In 1817, he was introduced to the now aging French political, economic, and socialist philosopher Henri Saint-Simon, becoming his disciple and secretary. During these years of fruitful collaboration, Comte produced many sketches and essays in close association with Saint-Simon, which would form the nucleus of all his later major works. However, in 1824, he chose to sever ties with his mentor due to a convoluted and somewhat disagreeable dispute surrounding the publication of one of his essays (not to be confused with the later, much more voluminous book with the same name), *Système de politique positive* [*System of Positive Polity*], in which he laid the very foundations of positive philosophy.

Ever the theorist, Comte sought to unify history, psychology, and economics within a scientific understanding of social life, determined to place these disciplines under the aegis of positivism. He advocated treating social phenomena with the same empirical rigor and thorough analysis as the natural sciences, aspiring to establish a cohesive methodology that would illuminate the underlying laws governing our society. From his study of the development of human intelligence he derived a “great fundamental law” – the Law of the Three Stages – which stated that human thought progressed through three distinct “methods of philosophizing”: the theological, or fictive stage; the metaphysical, or abstract stage; and finally, the scientific, or positive stage. Each reflecting a successive evolution in the way we explain and understand the world, moving from myth and supernatural mysteries, through abstract philosophical reasoning, to empirical and scientific inquiry (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, pp. 1f). In the *theological state*, the human mind seeks to understand the essential nature of beings, the first and final causes, the origin and purpose of all things – in short, the pursuit of absolute

knowledge. It assumes that all phenomena are the result of the direct and immediate action of supernatural beings, which substituted for the forces of nature. In the *metaphysical state*, which Comte considered a mere refinement of the theological one, the mind replaces the supernatural beings with abstract forces – abstractions inherent in all beings – believed to be capable of producing all phenomena. At this stage, the “explanation” of these phenomena involves simply relating each to its own abstract entity. And as British historian Stephen Gaukroger (2020, p. 186) pointed out: “The history of science is littered with examples of labelling masquerading as explaining [...]”. In the final, *positive state*, the mind abandons the futile quest for absolute notions – the origin and destiny of the universe, and the causes of phenomena – focusing instead on studying their laws. Reason and observation are the tools of this type of knowledge, and are used to explain facts by establishing connections between individual phenomena and broader general laws, the number of which continues to decrease as science progresses (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, p. 2).

Furthermore, Comte also attempted to establish a hierarchy of sciences, asserting that just as humanity advances through distinct stages, with each successive stage building upon, and being dependent on the achievements of its predecessors, so does scientific knowledge develop in phases, in accordance with “the great encyclopaedic law” which classifies all phenomena by their complexity and specificity (Comte, 1851/1875, p. 453). The former being concerned with the most general, simple, and abstract phenomena – those that are most distant from our direct experience and which influence all the others without being influenced in return. The latter focusing on the most particular, compound, and concrete phenomena – those that bear the most immediate relevance to the individual (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, p. 30). He observed that, from Francis Bacon to René Descartes to Galileo Galilei, four main categories of phenomena had been established: astronomical, physical, chemical, and physiological. However, he noted the conspicuous absence of social phenomena, which although closely related to physiological phenomena, he argued warranted their own distinct category (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, p. 7). Here, he deemed it necessary to introduce a new science to complete the host of human knowledge, namely *social physics* (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, p. 8). Recognizing the unique complexities and dynamics of social interactions and structures that could not be fully explained through the existing categories of natural sciences, this new field of social physics was intended to study the laws governing society in the same systematic way that natural sciences study the physical world. By positioning social phenomena within a scientific framework, this discipline would allow for the application of empirical methods to better understand human behaviours and, with it, the underlying structures of society. This would eventually evolve into what we now know as sociology. Although the proper term “sociology” can be traced back to the French abbot Emmanuel Joseph Sieyès, who coined it in an, at that time unpublished,

manuscript from 1780, it was Comte who later popularized and formally established it as its own distinct field.

What remained to be done, according to Comte, was to move beyond the “bastard positivism” of the late metaphysical stage in which many of the sciences were still situated and establish them firmly within the final stage of human knowledge – the positive stage (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, p. 246). But what was in effect the final purpose of positive philosophy? It was envisioned as a system that considered all observable phenomena as subject to invariable natural laws, abandoning the speculative search for first or ultimate causes. Instead, it focused on analysing the circumstances of phenomena with precision and connecting them through natural relations of similitude and succession. In this way, positive philosophy aimed to provide explanations not by asking *why* things happened, but by discerning *how* they happened, thus identifying regular patterns that allow for a better empirical understanding of the world (Comte, 1830–1842/1896, pp. 5f).

By the time of the publication of the first volume of his *Système de politique positive* [*System of Positive Polity*] in 1851, he established the hierarchy of sciences as follows: mathematics, astronomy, physics, chemistry, biology, and sociology (Comte, 1851/1875, pp. 33f). Though both here and in the *Catéchisme positiviste* [*Catechism of Positive Religion*] which appeared in the same year, Comte was rather preoccupied with a project to establish a “Religion of Humanity” within a so-called “Positive Church” (Comte, 1851/1875, p. 313). As with the earlier attempts to create a “Cult of Reason” during the French Revolution, Comte’s endeavour proved to be highly ambitious but ultimately futile. His efforts to reconcile scientific rationalism with a quasi-religious social order through a new secular, human-centered belief system did not achieve the lasting impact he had envisioned. Although it is worth noting that it did indeed leave a significant mark on many thinkers, schools of thought, secular and humanist organizations, political movements, and even state policies, just not at the level of universality that Comte desired.

Positivism, by virtue of its methodical rigor and its determination to systematize all knowledge through empirical observation, naturally invited an equally formidable counter-movement – *antipositivism*. This reaction, which emerged almost in parallel with the spread of positivism, sought to challenge its reductionist framework and reclaim the deeper complexity of human experience. Thinkers such as Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Karl Marx, Ferdinand Tönnies, Max Weber, and Georg Simmel rejected the positivist claim that all aspects of reality could be fully apprehended through the quantifiable and the observable alone. Instead, they emphasized the irreducibility of social, historical, and psychological dimensions, advocating for interpretive methods that could capture the nuanced interrelations of human existence and the evolving structures of society. Thus, antipositivism although diverse in its particular strands, emerged as a unified critique that sought to preserve the richness and multiplicity of the human

condition, resisting positivism's tendency toward abstraction and homogenization. Thus, after more than two millennia, the hold of metaphysical realism began to wane, giving way not only to positivism, but also to dialectical materialism and phenomenology as competing methodologies in philosophy.

DARWINISM, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL

Comte's *Système* was conceived as a grand intellectual synthesis aimed at demonstrating the universal applicability of natural laws across the entire spectrum of human understanding. Inspired by this ambitious vision, the British philosopher Herbert Spencer took to compiling his own monumental *System of Synthetic Philosophy* – a project that would occupy much of his lifetime – beginning its publication in 1855 and concluding only in 1896. Comte's earlier theory of sociocultural evolution, articulated through his Law of the Three Stages, laid the groundwork for Spencer's extension of evolutionary theory. He sought to propagate the principle of evolution beyond the field of biology and onto psychology, sociology – adopting into English Comte's term for this nascent discipline – and ethics, thereby proposing a unified metaphysical superstructure that could encompass both the natural and social orders. Each component of his *System* – published in parts largely out of sequence, similar to Hobbes' and which he subsequently expanded – aligned broadly with Comte's categorization of the sciences: *First Principles* in 1862, *The Principles of Biology* in 1864, *The Principles of Psychology* in 1855, *The Principles of Sociology* started in 1873 as a series called *Descriptive Sociology*, and *The Principles of Ethics*, the beginnings of which can be traced as early as 1842 in a series of letters on *The Proper Sphere of Government*. Collectively, these volumes served as an attempt to demonstrate that evolutionary dynamics govern not only organic and biological processes but also the unfolding complexities of human consciousness, the structuring of social institutions, and the trajectory of moral development. Thus, he sought to integrate every dimension of existence into a single, coherent philosophical system, bringing together nature and culture within the framework of evolutionary metaphysics.

Spencer comes across more as a syncretic thinker, weaving together different strands of evolutionary theories with a pronounced inclination toward Lamarckism, and only incidentally involved with fellow British naturalist Charles Darwin, whose works he read later in his career. In many respects, his approach can be seen as an intellectual continuation of the earlier principles proposed by the French zoologist Jean-Baptiste Lamarck, whom Darwin himself frequent references. Lamarckian inheritance posits that an organism can pass on to its progeny the traits it acquired through habitual use or disuse within its own lifetime – a concept that diverges fundamentally from the strictly biological inheritance emphasized by Darwin in his theory of evolution. Unlike innate physical traits that are encoded in

genes, Lamarckian traits represented acquired habits that were external to an organism's hereditary constitution. Such habits are cultivated and maintained within a distinct psychological or sociocultural environment, relying on the transmission of learned behaviours and practices rather than mutation and subsequent natural selection. Darwin engaged extensively with this notion of "inherited habits" in his most influential works, *On the Origin of Species* and *The Descent of Man*. While he did not explicitly embrace Lamarck's theories, he acknowledged that behaviours and habits developed through the use and disuse of certain faculties could have a notable impact on an organism's evolutionary trajectory. Though he maintained that in the end natural selection was the primary mechanism of evolution. He drew a distinction between instinct and habit, positioning the latter as behaviours that develop within a specific psychological environment and are sustained through repetition and learning. Instincts were innate, biological responses that emerged without conscious effort, while habits formed through practice and were modifiable over time. This difference implies that habits, unlike instincts, are deeply intertwined with the cognitive capabilities of the organism and are anchored in the virtualization capacities of the mind. For habits to establish themselves and propagate, they must exist within a mental ecosystem capable of supporting learning, memory, and behavioural reinforcement. Thus, while instincts are stable and inherited directly, habits are more fluid and require a context – both environmental and psychological – where they can be cultivated, shared, and transmitted. In Spencer's system, these acquired characteristics become instrumental in shaping social institutions, norms, and cultural practices, suggesting that human development is as much a matter of psychological adaptation as it is of physiological evolution.

Darwin's views on cultural evolution were rooted in the pragmatic necessities of survival, where even the most rudimentary technological advancements could mark the difference between a tribe's proliferation and its extinction. Material culture emerged as a direct response to the imperatives of survival, and once a new tool, method, or practice was developed, it spread rapidly through imitation. This imitation, however, was not merely a mechanical act but was driven by the instinctual self-preservation embedded within each member of the group. He posits that "if some one man in a tribe, more sagacious than the others, invented a new snare or weapon, or other means of attack or defence, the plainest self-interest, without the assistance of much reasoning power, would prompt the other members to imitate him; and all would thus profit" (Darwin, 1871/1981, p. 161). This suggests that cultural transmission in its initial stages required no sophisticated cognitive faculties or conscious planning, only the straightforward imitation of successful strategies that have demonstrated their utility in enhancing survival and reproduction. The cumulative effects of these imitative processes eventually lead to the establishment of more complex traditions and material cultures that become deeply intertwined with the tribe's identity and survival strategies. Darwin

reasoned that within a tribal setting, any novel discovery, innovation, or behavioural adaptation would confer a survival advantage, making it more likely to grow, dominate, and out-compete neighbouring tribes. Such a tribe would thus expand its influence, increasing the likelihood that other inventive individuals of superior abilities would emerge within it, fostering a positive feedback loop of cultural and intellectual advancement. This mechanism, he argued, was not limited to practical inventions but extended to the development of the arts as well. The continuous exercise and refinement of artistic skills, just as with technological or practical crafts, would contribute to the strengthening of the intellect, thereby enhancing not only the aesthetic sensibilities but also the cognitive capacities of the group as a whole. Culture, encompassing both material and immaterial aspects, must be understood as “socially learned behaviour” which is propagated through “social learning” – the process of replicating behaviours observed in others or acquiring them through direct instruction and shared experiences (Darwin, 1871/1981, p. 161). Such socially learned behaviours are thus distinct from purely instinctual responses, as they are transmitted not through genetic inheritance but through the intentional and communal sharing of knowledge, customs, and skills. This positions culture itself as an evolving phenomenon, shaped by both the creative impulses of individuals and the collective memory of the community, revealing the integral role of social interaction in the cultivation of intellectual and artistic advancements.

Emil du Bois-Reymond notably insisted that he had been the first in Germany to have recognized the revolutionary significance of Darwin’s theories and the first to speak openly in support of them in his 1876 lecture *Darwin versus Galvani* (Veit-Brause, 2001, p. 43). With this he challenged many traditional views, particularly in German academia. At the time, the German school of anthropology largely rejected monogenism – the idea that all humans shared a common origin – in favour of polygenism, which posited that different races had distinct origins. A stance which was in line with earlier thinkers such as Voltaire and David Hume.

Darwinism, although associated with Charles Darwin, is in actuality the product of the interpretations that his equally famous compatriot Herbert Spencer came up with after reading him. Particularly the concept of “survival of the fittest”, which became synonymous with Darwinism, originated in Spencer’s *Principles of Biology* (Spencer, 1864/1880, p. 444). It was Darwin who later adopted the phrase in the 1869 edition of his works. Spencer sought to apply Darwin’s principles well beyond biology, thus he turned Darwin’s biological research into a social theory that would leave a profound, if controversial, legacy in the human sciences. Although both Darwinism and Lamarckism have been largely superseded by the chromosomal theory of inheritance and modern genetics within the natural sciences, the principles of these theories, as popularized by Spencer, have found new life in the social sciences and humanities. Spencer exemplifies a broader intellectual tendency to greatly exaggerate the role of biological determinants and

to extend them indiscriminately into various domains of social life. By extrapolating Darwinian principles outside their appropriate scope, Spencer and his followers attempted to interpret complex social phenomena such as social hierarchies, cultural norms, and political institutions through the lens of natural selection and survival of the fittest. A drift which eventually led to the development of the concept of *Social Darwinism*, which was subsequently expanded upon into that of *Cultural Darwinism*. A theory rooted in the principles of Darwinian evolution which posits that cultural practices and beliefs are subject to a selection process analogous to biological evolution. This perspective argues that societies and cultures evolve over time through mechanisms of competition, adaptation and survival, stressing with this the manner in which prevailing cultural paradigms are shaped by their ability to withstand and endure the challenges of a constantly changing environment. Thus, cultural evolution became a reflection of the ongoing struggle for relevance in the face of changing social realities. And, like natural selection, it offered a justification for the (often deliberate) extinction or assimilation of certain cultures by other, more dominant ones, often framed as a consequence of the former's maladaptation.

Although influential and very popular in the latter half of the 19th century, Spencer has been criticized for his extreme reductionism and his tendency to obscure the nuanced interplay of historical, cultural, and psychological factors that define human society. His evolutionary understanding of the world, with its overemphasis on competition and adaptation, would provide a powerful conceptual toolkit for disciplines outside of biology that sought to explain the development of societies, cultures, and human behaviour. Consequently, although his scientific validity has since declined, many of his metaphors and analogies continue to shape the discourse of social progress, historical change and the dynamics of cultural evolution. A trend that many considered, and rightly so, to be actively dangerous.

VÖLKERPSYCHOLOGIE. THE MIND OF THE PEOPLE

In 1879, at the University of Leipzig, Wilhelm Wundt would be the first to found a formal laboratory for psychological research – the Institute for Experimental Psychology. As the name suggests, the investigations conducted at the institute were empirical and experimental in nature. Beginning the following year, his works here began playing a pivotal role in shaping the field of empirical psychology. Building on the discoveries of his mentor, German physicist and physician Hermann von Helmholtz, who measured the speed of reflex transmissions, Wundt sought to quantify the speed at which the brain processes nerve impulses by measuring reaction times. His goal was to measure cognitive operations, proposing that the sensory processes reflected in these measurements could correspond to intellectual operations (Gaukroger, 2020, p. 415).

From April 1891, Constantin Rădulescu-Motru – which came from the laboratory of another great pioneer, the French neuroscientist Jean-Martin Charcot – enrolled at the University of Leipzig with the specific aim of attending Wundt's courses and participating in his experiments (Schifirneț, 2003, p. 147). He would study here until 1893, when he received his doctorate with a thesis supervised by Wundt himself on the philosophy of Immanuel Kant titled *Zur Entwicklung von Kant's Theorie der Naturkausalität* [*On the Development of Kant's Theory of Natural Causality*]. During Motru's stay, Leipzig became a world-renowned centre for experimental psychology (Schifirneț, 2003, p. 149), that would attract many prominent intellectuals from various other disciplines, including the Russian neurologist Vladimir Mikhailovich Bekhterev, the French sociologist Émile Durkheim, the Austrian-Jewish German philosopher Edmund Husserl, the German sociologist, economist, and philosopher Ferdinand Tönnies, the Polish-born British anthropologist and ethnologist Bronislaw Malinowski, the American philosopher, sociologist, and psychologist George Herbert Mead, the Lithuanian-Jewish American anthropologist and linguist Edward Sapir, along with his student, the American linguist Benjamin Lee Whorf. Another Romanian, future sociologist Dimitrie Gusti would come to study at the University of Leipzig in 1900. Like Motru, Gusti was a frequent participant in Wundt's laboratory, and in 1904 completed his doctoral thesis, *Egoismus und Altruismus: Zur soziologischen Motivation des praktischen Willens* [*Egoism and Altruism: On the Sociological Motivation of Practical Will*] under his supervision. In 1893, yet another former student of Wundt's, the German-Romanian philologist and now psychologist Eduard Gruber, founded the first experimental psychology laboratory in Romania at the University of Iași. Unfortunately, Gruber's untimely demise in 1896 brought a premature end to his works. The mantle would pass on from 1897 to Motru at the University of Bucharest. By 1898, his courses would be formally consolidated and restructured as the Department of Experimental Psychology, and in 1906 these efforts culminated in the establishment of a new experimental psychology laboratory here. Nonetheless, the involvement of important Romanian intellectuals in Wundt's experimental psychology not only influenced the scope of psychological and sociological research in Romania but also facilitated the transmission of empirical research methods to Romanian academic circles. Thus, further consolidating Wundt's legacy in Romanian intellectual life during this period and, in turn, significantly shaping the development of social sciences in Romania, aligning them with the broader European currents.

However, Wundt recognized the limitations of applying his experimental practices to psychology, as these techniques were only effective for investigating the most elementary functions, such as reactions, perceptions, and sensations. The higher, more complex products of the mind required an entirely different approach, as they could not be recreated within the controlled conditions of a laboratory and could only be observed indirectly. In examining the broader question of the

relationship between the individual and the community, he emphasized that psychological “composites” were not the creations of the individual mind, but rather of the collective expressions of the community or the *Volk* – the people. For Wundt, sociology as a discipline was still an incomplete project, lacking a clear and established foundation. It did not qualify as a true philosophical discipline, as evidenced by the works of Auguste Comte and Herbert Spencer, but rather functioned as a veiled form of philosophy of history. Therefore, he dismissed both social psychology and sociology as insufficient, contending that they were excessively preoccupied with the immediate analysis of contemporary society. By failing to incorporate the more profound psychological insights and overlooking the developmental and historical trajectories that underlie the evolution of civilizations, these fields offered a disjointed perspective divorced from the broader narrative of human cultural progression. Consequently, in their existing state, they were incapable of providing “group psychology” with the requisite theoretical foundation (Klautke, 2013, p. 65). This realization led Wundt to advocate for the necessity of expanding individual psychology into the realm of cultural psychology, where the collective processes shaped by social interactions and communal life could be properly understood (Klautke, 2013, pp. 58f).

Early in his career, Wundt had developed an interest in *Völkerpsychologie*, a concept introduced by the post-Hegelian social philosophers Heymann Steinthal and Moritz Lazarus. In 1863 he published *Vorlesungen über die Menschen- und Tierseele [Lectures on Human and Animal Psychology]* following an “old idea of a comparative psychology of races and peoples” that had enticed him to conclude his study of psychology with an outline of anthropology and folk psychology focusing on language, myths, religion, customs and habits (Klautke, 2013, pp. 62f). The study, which was rather hastily compiled, was met with such poor reception that Wundt ultimately decided to temporarily shelve this project, redirecting his efforts toward experimental psychology, a field in which he would soon earn distinction and ultimately establish his lasting reputation. In 1900, Wundt would eventually revisit these themes, significantly expanding them through the publication of a massive work in 10 volumes titled *Völkerpsychologie: Eine Untersuchung der Entwicklungsgesetze von Sprache, Mythos und Sitte [Folk Psychology: An Inquiry into the Developmental Laws of Language, Myth, and Custom]*.

Wundt’s *Völkerpsychologie* draws heavily from Hegel’s earlier concept of *Volksgeist* – the spirit of a people. The distinction, as well as the direct relation, that Wundt established between them lies in the differentiation of psychology and sociology: psychology was concerned with the particularities of the individual, while sociology addressed groups of individuals, or what French anthropologist and sociologist Gustave Le Bon referred to as “the psychology of the masses”. This dual approach would be very influential to Constantin Rădulescu-Motru’s own understanding of the relationship between the two disciplines, viewing psychology as an integral part of a greater sociological setting. The common denominator in

both, according to these views, was the human person, understood not merely as a biological entity but as a being endowed with higher capacities and attributes – such as reason, morality, consciousness, and, most importantly, self-consciousness. This self-aware person was placed within a culturally established form of life, engaging in complex social relations with others who shared similar attributes, thereby integrating individual psychology into the larger, collective dynamics of societal existence.

KULTUR AND THE CULTURAL SELECTION THEORY

With the establishment of *Völkerpsychologie* through the efforts of Wilhelm Wundt we have finally arrived to the fundamental issues of the early 20th century – the amalgamation of culture with the “struggle for existence” found in German geographer and ethnographer Friedrich Ratzel’s principle of *Lebensraum*, and the development of the modern interpretations of geopolitics and biopolitics. Wundt, who had been politically active throughout his career, and a staunch liberal at that, sought to reconcile his psychological theories with a broader humanistic worldview. His orientations shaped not only his academic pursuits but also his political and social views. Thus, he championed the ideals of progress, rationality, and the cultivation of individual freedom within a socially cohesive framework. This ideological stance underpinned his emphasis on the development of communal consciousness through *Völkerpsychologie*, where he aimed to understand the cultural and historical dimensions of human societies without succumbing to deterministic or reductionist explanations. Despite his commitment to liberalism, Wundt’s ideas on collective consciousness and national identity would later be misappropriated by the more reactionary currents of the early 20th century. His approach to the relation between individual psychology and communal life, initially intended to demonstrate the organic development of cultural forms, was often distorted to serve the agendas of radical nationalists.

Wundt’s works would thus become entangled in the broader ideological struggles of the era, as an example of the intersection between scientific theories and their socio-political appropriations. This inadvertently laid the groundwork for constructs that would later prefigure the radicalization of nationalist thought, particularly in the Weimar Republic. The concept of *Kultur* became one of these focal points, serving as a repository for notions such as national identity and collective spirits. Following the trauma of the Great War, the 1920s saw a concentrated effort to distil a coherent national narrative from the apparent heterogeneity of intellectual paradigms. This period marked a transformation wherein *national characterology*, originally intended as a descriptive tool, evolved into a kind of metascience. It came to function as an organon for reconciling political ideologies with the collective mentality of the populace. As such, it

established an ostensibly scientific basis for delineating the so-called national essence, serving to justify and solidify particular political agendas. The competition among radical nationalist factions to monopolize this symbolic realm of national identity thus intensified, with various groups striving to define and control the narratives of a national *Volksgeist*, ultimately shaping the political and cultural discourse in ways that propelled the radical nationalists in various positions of power

On 17 January 1873, the German physician and anthropologist Rudolf Virchow gave a speech in front of the Prussian parliament in which he introduced the concept of *Kulturkampf*. From Virchow's particularly anti-Catholic rhetoric, *Kulturkampf* has since expanded to encompass a broader range of contexts. The term generally refers to a conflict between cultures, a "clash" or struggle for dominance over cultural identities either within a society or between different social groups. Typically, this struggle involves an element considered autochthonous clashing with one that is seen as allochthonous. On 27 March 1877, in Cologne, Du Bois-Reymond held an address at the Society for Scholarly Lectures titled *Kulturgeschichte und Naturwissenschaft* [*Cultural History and Natural Sciences*], setting the tone for yet another issue in this long list of determinations, namely the relationship between the natural sciences – *Naturwissenschaften* – and the human or cultural sciences – *Geistes* or *Kulturwissenschaften*. From this point onwards, not only natural philosophy had to be scientific, but culture as well (Veit-Brause, 2001, p. 44). The civilizational achievements of the German Empire had to be safeguarded, lest they perished under the threat of the upcoming age of excessive material interests and intellectual "trivialization" (Veit-Brause, 2001, pp. 44f). Du Bois-Reymond had proposed a novel theory regarding the fall of ancient civilizations, particularly the Greek and Roman Empires. He argued that they had experienced a disproportion between their technical and aesthetic achievements, especially when compared to other great civilizations of the time, like China (Du Bois-Reymond, 1877/1912, p. 581). The ancients' failure to advance the natural sciences at the same pace as their cultural and artistic proficiencies proved to be disastrous. And it was precisely this scientific lag, he claimed, was one of the most critical factors contributing to their eventual displacement by the incoming barbarians (Du Bois-Reymond, 1877/1912, p. 582). These remarks were made at a time when concerns about civilizational decline were widespread, spurred in part by the writings of French novelist and orientalist Arthur de Gobineau, whose works mostly focused on themes of racial degeneration. This obsession with civilizational decline would later be taken up and substantially elaborated by the German philosopher Oswald Spengler.

In Romania, Alexandru Dimitrie Xenopol stood as one of the earliest proponents of *Völkerpsychologie*. His innovative theory of history was rooted in a complex understanding of causality and seriality within the scope of ethnopsychology. He posited that the nation was not merely a political community

but an essential psycho-physiognomic matrix necessary for human existence, which, being rooted in a given territory, was shaped by the interaction with environmental factors such as climate and geography. These elements, he argued, influenced the physiological makeup of each nation, and in turn, this manifests in the distinct expressions of its national psyche (Trencsényi, 2012, p. 30). The particular (metaphorical) physiognomy of a nation then crystallizes into a unique repertoire of ideas and cultural forms. For him, these collective ideas formed in the minds of a people take shape through specific organs of the body, and the coagulation of said ideas finds its first articulation in language. The repetition of these ideas in recurring patterns and their integration into daily practices generate mores and customs, which therefore vary significantly among different nations. This accumulation of past experiences, preserved in the collective memory, forms what is called *tradition*, representing the living legacy of a people's past and the foundation upon which its current identity rests (Xenopol, 1872, p. 81). He distinguished between two dimensions within the national spirit: an inner, particular world, and a more universal domain. The former encompasses language, customs, traditions, and aesthetics – elements unique to each nation and reflective of its particular genius. The latter, however, extends beyond the boundaries of the nation to include general human pursuits, such as science, industry, and commerce, which are shared across cultures. It was the harmonious integration of these two realms that constituted the national spirit, a dynamic synthesis that bonded the individual to the nation's spiritual essence through what he poetically described as the love of one's motherland. This love was not directed towards the physical, "bare", land itself on which a nation was born and lives, but rather toward its immaterial legacies – the thoughts, traditions, and creative achievements – that have flourished within that particular territory. These elements together form the nationality. They support each other, grow, rise and fall together. Thus, the development of a nation was contingent on the vitality of its internal cultural forces and its commitment to the spirit that animated its collective existence (Xenopol, 1872, p. 82).

Hungarian historian Balázs Trencsényi (2012, p. 32) described these endeavours as the "[...] Romantic pattern of extracting the national essence from the people and projecting it back onto the nation". A process, emblematic of 19th century Romantic nationalism that involved a comprehensive reinterpretation of national tradition, striving to define the inner soul of the nation through an exploration of its cultural, historical, and psychological roots. Such efforts sought to capture a purportedly timeless national spirit from the customs, folklore, and linguistic expressions of the people, and subsequently elevate it to the status of an ontological foundation for national identity. These intellectual pursuits were, in effect, attempts to construct a coherent narrative that could provide political stability and legitimacy to a nation. By mapping out the contours of the so-called national psyche these thinkers aimed to define the spiritual core of their

communities, thereby creating a framework that linked individual and collective identity to a shared historical and metaphysical essence. The notion of a “national ontology” thus emerged, suggesting that nations possess a distinctive, enduring character that could be systematically uncovered, articulated, and projected onto the larger body politic, reinforcing a sense of national cohesion and continuity. This project of *Volkskunde* – folkloristics, however, risked essentializing the nation, often transforming the fluid, multifaceted realities of communal life into static, mythologized constructions.

There is an argument for the cultural selection theory that certain cultures are better suited to the proliferation of its carriers. For example, a culture that offers no impediment to technological evolution is more likely to survive than one with technophobic characteristics. Or a culture with an optimistic outlook on life is more likely to survive than cultures plagued by depression such as the French, German and Russian, or suicide as in the aforementioned nations, as well as those of East Asia. In this respect there was a conflict between the Polish-born British anthropologist and ethnologist Bronislaw Malinowski and his colleague Alfred Reginald Radcliffe-Brown. Malinowski’s psychological functionalism argued that culture was intended in order to meet the needs of individuals rather than the needs of society as a whole. He claimed that when the needs of the individuals who constitute a given society are satisfied, the needs of that society as a whole are satisfied as well. For Malinowski, understanding a society required taking into account the feelings and motives of its members, as these subjective elements were essential to the way that society functioned. He believed that the internal states of individuals – such as desires, emotions, and intentions – played a critical role in shaping cultural practices and social institutions, which in turn worked to meet both psychological and biological needs. Thus, the institutions of certain societies should not be explained as hangovers from olden times and dismissed as irrational barriers to progress. Rather, their customs and beliefs serve essential, functional purposes within their communities, addressing certain specific needs and ensuring social cohesion. Radcliffe-Brown’s summed up his theory as defining society in terms of structure and process, interconnected by functions and Malinowski’s as a theory of culture derived from individual biological needs (Radcliffe-Brown, 1949, p. 322). South African anthropologist Adam Kuper summarized the theories of the two as follows: Malinowski gradually arrived at the conclusion that the subject was not about the social relations and interactions of human beings, but about culture. And a culture was, for him, a set of tools designed to satisfy biological needs. In contrast, Radcliffe-Brown’s approach, which would come to be termed structural-functionalism, shifted the emphasis away from biological functions to social functions and how these functions contribute to the maintenance and stability of the social order (Kuper, 1973/2015, p. 39).

Constantin Rădulescu-Motru emphasized the vital role that culture had played as an indispensable condition in the advancement of nations, especially to

those emerging from a state of barbarism, as he called it. According to him, culture served as the reflective surface upon which the social consciousness of a nation was crystallized, embodying its ultimate purpose and direction. Within the realm of culture, human actions transcend mere immediacy, acquiring a higher meaning – they become historical. A nation without culture has no history, because it has no criteria by which to assess the value of past events (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 5). However, not all nations enjoy an equal degree of cultural development. For this reason, he began an examination in which he catalogued European cultures as *true cultures*, *semicultures* and *pseudocultures*. Semiculture and pseudoculture represented intermediate states between barbarism and true culture. There are nations that have yet to achieve a true form of culture, although they have not remained in barbarism either. These have become a form of semiculture (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 8f). Within them we encounter a disparity of spiritual tendencies, and a lack of harmony and continuity in its social consciousness. However, this is not the result of an intentional evil, Motru claims, but rather of something that is yet unfinished (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 15). Pseudoculture, or false culture, can be distinguished quite clearly from semiculture. A nation in a state of pseudoculture possesses all the spiritual values we find in other cultured nation: religion, science, art, technical innovations; and sometimes even in a more brilliant form than those of true cultured people, however, in appearance only (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 9). In actuality, they are dependent on foreign influences. The turmoil in their public life demonstrated a deficit of originality, a lack of understanding of their soul, and a vacuum of depth. And nowhere is this more obvious than in the precarious political organization which hides behind it “the misery of reality despite its external pomp” (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 10). Of these two, pseudoculture is particularly harmful because it falsifies both the soul of the society and the souls of individuals living thereof, reducing them to a ridicule. Semiculture, fortunately, does not have the same effects, because it still maintains the possibility of a future better development (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 16). Nonetheless, Motru argued that any of these are better than barbaric societies, in which the struggle for existence is more bitter and ruthless, often resulting in bloodshed (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 12). The Romanian people have lived in a state of semiculture until the beginning the 19th century. The last generation shaped by this spirit was the one that achieved the Union of 1859. From here on, the soul of our people became alienated from its past. Attempting to emulate as closely as possible the nations of Western Europe instead of experiencing an authentic, indigenous development. Our process of unifying our national consciousness did not culminate in the creation of a true culture, but was veered into a pseudoculture “with fictitious and deceitful political proclamations” (Rădulescu-Motru, 1904, p. 18). A state in which it would find itself well into the Interwar period.

A similar concept would later be introduced by Oswald Spengler – that of *historical pseudomorphosis* (Spengler, 1922/1926, p. 189). He based his theory on

the concept of the same name from geology, which refers to a rock formation composed of a certain mineral but taking the appearance of another. These, he said, exist as distorted forms whose inner structures contradict their outer shape. By extending this analogy, he designated those cases in which an older but foreign culture dominated in a territory to such an extent that it did not allow a younger, indigenous culture to take shape or to attain pure and specific forms of expression, nor even to fully develop its own self-consciousness (Spengler, 1922/1926, p. 189).

THE PSYCHOLOGY OF THE ROMANIAN PEOPLE

In the modern history of Romania, there are three major efforts that stand out in the attempt to decipher the enigma of our national psyche. The first, Dumitru Drăghicescu's *Din psihologia poporului român* [*From the Psychology of the Romanian People*], which appeared in 1907, marked a momentous attempt at exploring the historical, cultural, and social determinants of the Romanian mentality. Despite its ambitious scope, however, it faced an unwelcoming reception, receiving harsh criticism – perhaps unfairly excessively so – for its methodological shortcomings. As a result, the project was abandoned after only the first volume. The second and most sustained attempt came from Constantin Rădulescu-Motru. His investigation began in 1906 with *Psihologia martorului* [*The Psychology of the Witness*], followed by *Psihologia industriașului* [*The Psychology of the Industrialist*] in 1907, and *Psihologia ciocoismului* [*The Psychology of the Boyars*] in 1908, published in the immediate aftermath of the bloody peasant uprising. Through these incisive studies, he sought to meticulously dissect the socio-cultural categories that shaped Romanian society at the time, revealing a subtle and complex portrait of its collective character. This, combined with his political writings, displayed a thorough commitment in identifying the social dynamics and class tensions that were becoming increasingly noticeable since the turn of the century. In 1919, at the height of the Russian Civil War, he published *Din psihologia revoluționarului* [*From the Psychology of the Revolutionary*]. Here, he extended his inquiry into the psychological substratum of political upheavals, delving into the mindset that drove the revolutionary consciousness and exploring the intricate relationship between social discontent and ideological fervour which were by now also making their presence felt in the Kingdom of Romania. Earlier, in 1910, he had embarked on a more cyclopaedic project aimed at constructing a broader framework for a national psychology in *Sufletul neamului nostru. Calități bune și defecte* [*The Soul of our Nation. Good Qualities and Flaws*]. Here he examined the virtues and vices of the Romanian ethos, meticulously analysing the deeper traits that shaped the nation's spiritual and cultural identity. At the 12 February 1937 session of the Romanian Academy, Motru delivered a lecture titled *Psihologia poporului român* [*The Psychology of the Romanian People*]

(Schifirneț, 2004, p. 512). It was to be published later as “a brochure”, as Romanian philosopher Constantin Noica called it, albeit one that succeeded in synthesizing decades of research of social and cultural ethnopsychology into a comprehensive summary (Schifirneț, 2004, p. 224). This enumeration is far from exhaustive, as numerous of his writings inevitably touch upon this theme in a sporadic yet recurring fashion. The third major exploration of the subject came much later, in 2015, with *Psihologia poporului român* [*The Psychology of the Romanian People*] by contemporary Romanian psychologist Daniel David. Unlike its predecessors, his took the form of a cognitive-experimental monograph – the most extensive and methodologically sophisticated study of the Romanian mentality to date. Though not as focused on historical or philosophical discourses, his approach is distinct through its empirical rigor, incorporating a collection of both past and present metrics as well as contemporary psychological theories. This can be seen as both a continuation and an evolution of the earlier efforts, merging classical insights with modern scientific methodology.

It would, indeed, have been fitting to include the contributions of Dimitrie Gusti, in particular his sociological monographic project which attempted to provide an authentic depiction of Romanian rural life, and with this taking a revolutionary step in the study of our national character. For the present purpose, however, we turn our attention to Constantin Rădulescu-Motru. *Psihologia poporului român* was not a mere academic exercise but was intended to serve as a prelude to a larger project. Its functional premise was closely tied to the political climate leading up to the December 1937 elections – a period marked by an extreme rise in social tension and the need for ideological reorientation. It came following, and complemented, a scheme that had been taking shape since 1934 with a series of articles, including the article-manifesto *Românismul* [*Romanianism*], which appeared in the July 1935 issue of *Revista Fundațiilor Regale* [*The Royal Foundations Magazine*]. This, alongside three earlier articles – *Nașterea spirituală a secolului nostru* [*The Spiritual Birth of our Century*] in May 1934, *Reabilitarea spiritualității* [*The Rehabilitation of Spirituality*] in November 1934, *Realizările spirituale* [*Spiritual Accomplishments*] in March 1935 – would form the core of *Românismul. Catehismul unei noi spiritualități* [*Romanianism. The Catechism of a New Spirituality*]. Although in many respects these writings represented a departure from Motru’s earlier works, whose primary aim was to offer a normative analysis of the Romanian character, here he articulated a design for the revitalization of the national ethos – one that sought to redefine Romanian collective identity and spirituality and to align it with what he perceived to be its historical vocation and projected destiny. In doing so, he aspired to construct a cohesive philosophical system that would lay the groundwork for a spiritual and cultural regeneration of the nation, deeply rooted in its traditions yet oriented

towards its unascertainable future. His vision would ultimately be appropriated and transformed into the ideological program of the National Renaissance Front, whose foremost theorist he was. However, for this new bio-political understanding of the nation it was first necessary to establish new sciences as well, such as anthropometry, racial biology, characterology, psycho-ethics, or the science of labour rationalization (Rădulescu-Motru, 1934–1935/1939, p. 95). However, mentality is a deep-seated complex of beliefs, values, and attitudes, and such a profound change in our collective soul as the one that Motru intended could not be achieved in one or two generations, but only under absolute exceptional circumstances and over a prolonged period of time. Thus, it becomes evident that he has not succeeded in his enterprise, and that his project remained little more than a romanticized myth of the nation's much-anticipated spiritual renewal.

The aim of social psychology, he believed, was to determine and explain the collective spiritual characteristics of a population. These characteristics in turn were conditioned by three main factors: the population's biological heritage, the geographical environment which it inhabited, and the institutional configurations it had developed over the course of its historical evolution (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 5). The interplay between innate predispositions, ecological influences, and the legacy of past developments that structure the social consciousness of a nation interweave to form a distinct psycho-social identity. Naturally, humans come into immediate contact with the physical elements of their environment, but this interaction is never purely instinctual, rather, it is invariably mediated through the interface of a socially acquired understanding of their actions (Rădulescu-Motru, 1908/1984, p. 360). This enables communities to not just react to their environment but to imbue their actions with meaning, creating a symbolic landscape that is not limited to a physical reality, but is also a repository of shared memory and identity shaped by language, traditions, and inherited concepts. Thus, nature becomes both a material reality and a culturally constructed space, wherein every action is, consciously or unconsciously, an expression of the shared patterns of thought that shapes the collective experience, turning simple survival strategies into culturally determined behaviours. With the introduction of the new mining law in 1929, Motru considered it opportune to reflect on the nature of nationalism, providing a sensible perspective that aligned with the, at the time, modern understanding of the interdependence between human society and its natural environment. He argued that "[...] the Romanian people cannot live without the land on which they were born, you cannot send this people to live in a land other than the one in which they were born, you cannot send them elsewhere because they would no longer have the national character of the Romanian people" (Rădulescu-Motru, 1929b, p. 5). The link between a population and their native land was not merely a matter of historical continuity or sentimental attachment as proposed by German sociologist Georg Simmel, it was a foundational element of their collective identity, inseparable from the broader context of their economic, social, and cultural

existence. The very essence of national character was thus rooted in the environment that shaped and sustained it, making the land not just a geographic backdrop to be exploited but a constitutive element and vital factor in the formation of the national psyche. Thus, to the struggle for resources, we had now to consider a struggle for national identity. In any territory other than our own, we would cease to be Romanians. Severed from its native habitat, a nation would not only lose its economic base but also the cultural and spiritual matrix which defined its unique character. However, the characteristics of a nation were determined not just by the spiritual dispositions and biological aptitudes of its individuals, but also by its political environment in which it finds itself – its territory determines its economic life and, and its neighbours, its political and cultural life (Rădulescu-Motru, 1936/1939, p. 28). Just as with individuals, the way in which a nation perceives itself often diverges from the image it projects to others. Thus, a nation's identity emerges not only from internal reflections, but from a continuous dialectic between its national self-perception and its representations by those who observe it from the outside.

Without further ado, let us see what the psychology of the Romanian people looks like through Constantin Rădulescu-Motru's eyes and whether his portrayal has managed to hold its relevance after all these years. We can set the tone of his analysis with the sad remark that "[...] there is nothing in the world of an easier nature, metaphysical ideas, mystical speculations, literary or artistic schools of dubious originality, that does not immediately find admirers and imitators in Romania" (Rădulescu-Motru, 1944/1996, p. 250f). For him, the quintessential trait of the Romanian ethos is an almost complete absorption of the individual's soul into the collective spirit of the group. A phenomenon he labels as *gregarism*. He contrasts this sociological gregariousness as a disposition opposed to the idea of *solidarity*. Solidarity being the result of conscious self-sacrifice, the culmination of the moral elevation of the will, and the final stage of cultural and ethical development – the very telos of a society's moral evolution (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 16). It represented a harmony achieved through the internal struggle and self-mastery of the individual – a genuine individualization through "[...] the acknowledgment of others, after each has known themselves" (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 17). Conversely, gregarism is not a product of any deliberate striving but emerges as a passive, almost mechanical harmony of souls, a state imposed by external circumstances and ancestral traditions, persisting even in the absence of culture, and often predating it. It is merely the aggregate of minds uncritically reflecting one another, an echo of conformity that reverberates through a society of undifferentiated souls. Gregarism operates through imitation, spreading effortlessly across its members. Thus, a society with a gregarious soul is a social organism driven not by a consciously shared purpose, but by an instinctive and primeval cohesiveness that precludes the very differentiation necessary for genuine solidarity (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 17).

This gregarism of our soul, Motru argues, has served in the past as our nation's most potent instrument of perseverance, and its most appropriate weapon. It was precisely through this collective disposition that the unity of language and its ecclesiastical bond were able to be preserved over the generations (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 19). Through the difficult circumstances of our history, in which our nation had to face myriads of adversities, this gregarious spirit had been a genuine blessing (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 20). Through sheer force of imitation, Romanians were able to coalesce as a unified polity, resisting the pressures exerted from all sides by external threats. What emerges was a nation endowed with the virtues of the group, but not the quality of distinct personalities. However, it found in this unity the fortitude necessary to survive and endure (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 20). Gregarism, although it obstructed the differentiation of individual identities and, by extension, the proliferation of a richer cultural life, nevertheless played an essential role in ensuring the continuity of the Romanian nation. With all its limitations, it maintained the collective integrity of a culture, weak as it might have been, in an age when such cohesion was imperative for survival, whereas a different society might have fractured under the weight of historical turbulences (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, pp. 19f).

Gregarism, should not be regarded as a form of moral deficiency or as a stigma one should be ashamed of, rather, it is an integral stage in the development of all nascent nations. It is a preliminary phase that precedes the emergence of a distinct national consciousness. Motru draws a parallel between the Romanians and the Germans, both of whom, despite their continued historical presence on European soil, only began to articulate their national identities in the aftermath of their respective political unifications under the aegis of Romantic nationalism – Romania in 1859 and Germany in 1866, respectively 1871. What would indeed be lamentable was if one nation was to cling indefinitely to this condition, remaining enmeshed in gregariousness and incapable of transcending it (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 17). To linger in gregarism would be to forgo the transformative potential of maturity and to remain perpetually suspended in a state of arrested national adolescence.

However, not all are capable of cultivating a national culture. Spirituality is not simply a product of the passage of time. Some populations have existed for millennia without institutional structures taking root in the fabric of their collective souls. They exist in a state of perpetual infancy, their spiritual essence remaining stagnant – sometimes due to hereditary biological constraints, and sometimes shaped by the immobility imposed by their geographical environment. Thus, social psychology, whose objective is to investigate the inner life of social organisms, is faced with a challenge when it examines the soul of a population lacking a “spiritual armature”, because its object of study is reduced to examining rudimentary, half-biological expressions of consciousness (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 7).

Fellow Romanian philosopher Lucian Blaga most notably opposed this position. He rejected the linear, and necessary teleological model of cultural evolution which posits that the development of a culture is a straightforward progression from an initial, undeveloped phase toward a state of maturity. Motru, adhering to a positivist worldview, saw gregarism as a transient stage that a young nation must necessarily outgrow in order to achieve a fully differentiated and solidified cultural identity. In contrast, Blaga offered a more nuanced, non-linear conception of cultural evolution. He introduces a dual typology of cultures: *eternal cultures* and *historical cultures*. Eternal cultures are those characterized by a timeless, mythopoetic consciousness, existing in a perpetual state of organic unity and self-sufficiency. They are not concerned with the historical self-assertion or the outward differentiation that historical cultures seek. Instead, they are grounded in an archetypal symbolism that conveys a unique metaphysical ethos, largely resistant to the forces of historicity. He argued that the transition from an eternal culture to a historical culture was not a necessary or inevitable outcome. While all major cultures may experience this transformation, it was not a causal relationship or a uniform evolutionary pattern. Rather, the two phases were autonomous, each possessing its own inner logic and ontological structures. For him, historical cultures were not inherently superior to eternal cultures. The transition from one to the other did not signify progress in a normative sense but rather a shift in the modality of a people's self-expression. He contended that cultural development could not be measured along a single continuum of immaturity and maturity. Instead, the eternal and historical phases represented two qualitatively distinct paradigms. The evolution of a people's soul, therefore, was not a question of "leaving behind" one stage in favour of a higher one, but rather a metamorphosis into a different state of being, governed by its own principles and imperatives. The maturity of a culture, for him, did not consist in its historical self-assertion, but rather in its capacity to embody a unique mode of existence, whether eternal or historical, according to its own metaphysical structures (Blaga, 1937/2011, p. 332). A culture can willingly choose to remain in its eternal phase for extended periods of time, and, indeed, some never leave this particular moment in their development. This state, which Blaga metaphorically describes as an "enclosed territory" becomes self-sufficient, an "autarchic duration" whose temporal unfolding is inwardly focused and cantered within itself (Blaga, 1937/2011, p. 333). Far from being a provisional or immature phase awaiting the arrival of historical self-consciousness, this cultural state asserts its own form of sovereignty – a sovereignty that is not defined by conquest, expansion, or external affirmation, but by its rootedness in a symbolic and metaphysical order that transcends the linear flow of historical time. In this sense, the "childhood" of such a culture is not merely an absence of maturity; it is a conscious withdrawal into a hermetically sealed inner world where myths, symbols, and values take precedence over historical action and outward engagement. The boundaries of this cultural territory

are not political or geographical, but ontological, establishing a space where time flows differently, where tradition is not merely preserved but continuously re-enacted in a self-referential cycle. This form of self-contained autonomy can endure indefinitely, insulated from external disruptions and guided by its own internal logic. These eternal cultures exist in a state of timeless maturity, even if, from the perspective of historical cultures, they appear to have not yet entered into the fullness of historical life. Their resistance to external pressures to evolve or transform is thus not a sign of immaturity, but a reflection of their fundamental autonomy, a temporality that is complete unto itself. In this context, the eternal phase was not a failure to grow but a deliberate choice to inhabit a different temporal and existential plane – one where the culture exercises “full sovereignty within its borders” (Blaga, 1937/2011, p. 333).

From this catalogue of “qualities” that Motru identified as defining the Romanian people, we can enumerate a few other notable traits. There is a paradoxical duality – a tension between collective valour and individual weakness. Romanians exhibit remarkable courage and vigour when acting as a collective, but when isolated, this strength dissipates. The gregarious nature of the Romanian soul, he contended, manifested itself in an almost reflexive tendency to imitate, “like sheep”, the actions and attitudes of those around us. This inclination resulted in a psychological dependency on the group, leading to an overemphasis on external validation and a corresponding absence of individual self-assertion. Motru illustrated this by contrasting two situations: in war – the battlefield and in peace – professional labour. In war, where individuals stand “shoulder to shoulder”, the Romanians displayed an indomitable spirit, drawing confidence and energy from the surrounding camaraderie (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 18). Yet, in the domain of individual professional ventures, where one is isolated and must rely on their own resources, there was a discernible lack of diligence, focus, and responsibility. This discrepancy, he suggested, was a consequence of an underdeveloped personal sense of duty and self-discipline – traits that, when present, are cultivated not innately but through the expectations and provisions of the group. This absence of individual resolve also translated into a lack of commitment in upholding personal convictions. Romanians, he observed, are quick to express impassioned opinions within the security of a group, but the courage to defend these views diminishes significantly when faced alone. Our national temperament, therefore, is characterized by a curious dichotomy: highly reactive and impressionable, “easily kindled like a fire of straw”, yet incapable of sustaining this ardour due to a lack of personal resolution (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 18). For this reason, we often experience severe spiritual crises (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 18). We are prone to radical swings of sentiment – periods of intense but short-lived enthusiasm, followed by rapid disillusionment and a reversion to passivity. We have a tendency to succumb too easily to the impulses of a crude nationalism – propelled by collective emotion rather than grounded in a reasoned and stable ideology

(Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 18). And we too readily answer the call of any pretend “holy war” against foreign nationals and their perceived malicious influences (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 19).

The character of the Romanian people, as he points out, vacillates between a strong desire for assertiveness held in place by a penchant for eagerly adopting foreign forms. We have a pensive compulsion to appropriate the cultural goods that we see in the nations of the Occident. This emulation was not merely the adoption of superficial behaviours and the internalization of external cultural models, rather, it was symptomatic of a deeper uncertainty in the search for authenticity and self-definition. Motru remarked that on the international stage we want to overcome the foreigners in trade and industry, we want to live a political life with a parliamentary regime, and we want to have an original culture of our own, all while retaining the old habits of our gregarious souls. This assortment of antics makes us appear not as strong individualities, distinguished in our aptitudes, but weak and homogeneously amateurish, wavering and faltering wordsmiths (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 22). This dilemma is emblematic of a deeper philosophical struggle: the conflict between authenticity and assimilation, between self-assertion and the gravitational pull of dominant cultural paradigms. This tension shaped not only the individual psyche but also the broader national character, situating Romania in a perpetual state of becoming – torn between the desire for self-definition and the seductive allure of established foreign archetypes. As such, the character of the Romanian people, as Motru perceives it, was one caught in an ongoing existential crisis. A restless spirit that seeks to assert itself, yet, at each turn, finds itself measured against, and often overshadowed by, the forms and standards of others. He distinguished between the autonomous, institutionalized individualism of the Occident and the peculiar form it takes in Romania. In Western societies, he asserts, individualism is a generative force – a dynamic reagent that moulds economic and social life, fuelling innovation, entrepreneurship, and the construction of robust institutions. It is a creative energy that channels personal initiative into collective structures. By contrast, the Romanian form of individualism, he argues, is less an outward expression of personal agency than an inward, self-centred withdrawal. This individualism, rather than serving as a foundation for communal or institutional development, becomes a symptom of isolation – “[...] simply a subjective reaction, an egocentrism, under the influence of the hereditary biological factor” (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 12). This disparity was perpetuated by the archaic structures of the Romanian state, which he claims have historically stifled the development of true autonomy and civic-mindedness. By inhibiting the cultivation of institutions that might nurture genuine individual initiative, the state has perpetuated a kind of systemic inertia, locking Romanian society into a form of individualism that is reactive rather than proactive, defensive rather than constructive. Thus, the very architecture of the Romanian state, he argued, had kept its people in a cycle where the notion of selfhood is fragmented,

leading to a culture where personal advancement is often seen in opposition to, rather than in service of, the collective good. This necessitated the development of a mature national character – one capable of harmonizing individuality with communal responsibility. Only then, he implied, could Romanian individualism become a creative force akin to its Western counterpart, generating institutions that reflected the active participation of autonomous, self-determined individuals in the public life, rather than perpetuating a stagnant cycle.

Another paradoxical tendency within the Romanian psyche is that while the collective soul is shaped by gregarism, the individual, in contrast, harbours a pronounced predilection for solitude and self-sufficiency. Though we are drawn to the safety and identity of the group, our instinctual desire is to retreat into private spaces where we can exercise undisturbed authority over our affairs. In familial and domestic matters, this manifested as a desire for absolute autarky. Motru observed that, regardless of the size or value of one's property, Romanians take pride in the notion that whatever little assets they have, it is theirs. The emphasis is less on the accumulation of wealth or status, and more on the satisfaction of being an unchallenged master over one's own domain, however modest it may be (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 11). This image of the self as a solitary autarch, reigning over a small, insular world, reveals a particular kind of individualism whose autonomy is circumscribed within the intimate sphere of the household, rather than expressed through civic or social engagement. Motru's insight here is that, while Romanians may appear socially gregarious, there is a latent desire for isolation that confuses their interactions with both the public sphere and each other. This disposition toward a kind of insular individualism gave rise to an ambivalence that continues to shape the attitudes towards authority and belonging of Romanians till this day. This form of individualism, Motru claimed, leads to a propensity for unruliness, sometimes bordering on outright anarchy. While one might expect such a strong sense of autonomy to foster a spirit of entrepreneurship and a drive for economic independence, the overly traditional Romanian ethos lacks the energetic independence that fuels capitalist enterprises in the Occident. Instead, it turns inward, resulting in an aversion to hierarchical structures and an unwillingness to submit to any external authority (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 11).

The bourgeois spirit, defined by personal initiative, self-discipline, and a willingness to partake in the creation of institutions, that is the bedrock of modern capitalist societies, Motru suggested, was conspicuously absent in Romania, especially among the rural population, which formed the backbone of the nation's demographic at the time. The traditional Romanian villager was deeply rooted in a communal way of life that prioritized local bonds and the maintenance of inherited customs over the competitive attitudes of capitalism. The economic and social independence that one might associate with a thriving middle class was not only lacking but also viewed as an alien concept that could potentially disrupt the gregarious equilibrium of the village community. Thus, it is unsurprising that

enterprising individuals, the archetypal self-made men which drive Western economic models, rarely emerge from the midst of Romanian society. Risk-taking and innovation are perceived with scepticism, if not outright disdain. The Romanian peasant, who cherishes his own household above all, sees no value in venturing beyond his immediate surroundings to engage with a broader economic system that seems fundamentally at odds with his parochial worldview. Consequently, the individualism that might elsewhere lead to prosperity here crystallizes into a passive resistance to change and a preference for the familiar rhythms of a static, tightly-knit communal life (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 11).

Motru reassures us that his rhetoric, though apparently harsh, should not be discouraging. The real danger, he warned, lies in the misconception that Romanians lack any redeeming merit or virtue whatsoever, which is far from the truth. Instead of seeking to emulate others, it is imperative to direct our attention to harnessing those good qualities that are also present in us. He identified perseverance and patience as fundamental pillars of the Romanian ethos. Despite an innate conservatism and attachment to tradition, Romanians possess an intrinsic perseverance in their pursuits, often preferring to bide their time and allow circumstances to ripen before attempting to reap the results of their labours. These traits, he suggested, were representative of a people who understand time differently, prioritizing stability over quick and volatile gains. This resilience was complemented by what he described as a distinctive technical ingenuity. Far from being a passive or stagnant conservatism, the traditionalism of the Romanians is dynamic and adaptable, able to improvise and find new resources despite the constraints of their environment. This particular vitality was what, in his opinion, conferred us the potential to secure for our nation a place in the Europe of the future (Rădulescu-Motru, 1937, p. 15).

Yet these qualities could not be exploited to their full potential as there was a significant and insurmountable incongruity between the hereditary factor of the nation and its institutional one. As a result of this unsuccessful pairing, the native character of the Romanian people has been distorted by the flawed institutional life indiscriminately imported from abroad by a political class disconnected from the realities of the common man. This misalignment manifested most starkly in the education system, the aim of which, according to Motru, was to level every child with the same mentality, all learning the same things, as if we were not inherently gifted with a uniform enough mentality (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 22). The very structure of Romanian education subordinated critical thinking to a mechanistic uniformity, prioritizing the reproduction of a shared set of beliefs and values over the cultivation of individual judgment. The ideology of education in Romania, especially rural education, had been shaped not by an organic understanding of local needs but by the misguided ambitions to elevate the nation's image in the eyes of "civilized" foreigners. Owing to a crude demagoguery, this borrowed curriculum, designed more for external validation than for genuine autochthonous

development, has further alienated the rural population, who emerged from this process having learned what is of little practical use to them. The Romanian peasantry that formed the bulk of the nation, was misunderstood and misrepresented by the institutions that were supposed to serve them. Rather than nurturing their distinct spirituality and economic patterns, the schools produced a superficial mimicry of Western bourgeois ideals. The outcome of which was a generation of rural youth caught in a profound contradiction – they were schooled in the rhetorics of individual initiative but constrained by the deeply ingrained collective traditions of their communities. The adult population of the Romanian villages, on the contrary, long habituated to a collective work ethics, lacked the incentive to deviate from the established social inertia. Every individual did what they thought everyone else might do. They did not have the courage to start any enterprise, except in accordance with the limits fixed by custom. For the Romanian peasant, to step out of line, was not only unconventional, but a sign of outright madness (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 16). The situation was no different for their children. They were thought in school to be enterprising, in a superficial sense, only to find that, upon graduating, the weight of tradition reasserted itself, neutralizing whatever proficiencies they may have acquired. And their efforts subjected to the same binding forces of custom that they inherited from their ancestors in the village (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, p. 17). All this was at odds with scientific pedagogy, which affirmed that the peasant was not a reduced bourgeois, a mere proto-citizen awaiting transformation into a modern subject, but a whole man possessing a different spirituality and with entirely other interests at heart, and whom the Romanian politician, himself distorted, continued to groom to the measure befitting the bourgeois (Rădulescu-Motru, 1934–1935/1939, p. 85). This discord was not merely a theoretical matter but a practical one. The inability to bridge the gap between inherited dispositions and imposed structures resulted in a cultural stagnation that suppressed the authentic development of the Romanian spirit. A system that failed to acknowledge the spiritual particularities of its population could not have cultivated a genuine culture or a stable society.

Of the Church, the other institution involved with education, especially the non-formal spiritual and moral instruction of the Romanian people, Motru held an even worse opinion. Far from serving as a nurturing environment for the cultivation of personal reflection, it acted as a rather repressive force, if not outright hostile to individual forms of expression. Instead of fostering spiritual development, the Church, through its rigid structures and practices, actively discouraged any attempt at individualization. Encouraging the faithful to engage with the Scriptures – reading during the priest's service – in the absence of other formal institutions, could, he believed, have served as a rudimentary form of public education. Especially in a rural environment where illiteracy remained widespread. It would offer parishioners the opportunity to get personally acquainted with the texts and to cultivate the habit of independent thought. Yet, as he points out with

dismay, this possibility was precluded by the Church's insistence on uniformity of belief and practice. He noted the tacit policy that "[i]n the service of our church there must be no opportunity for the individualization of the soul!" (Rădulescu-Motru, 1910, pp. 22f). Where other traditions might see religious services as moments of personal communion and introspection, in the Romanian Church, the service becomes a space where the soul's voice is silenced, submerged under the weight of ritualistic conformity. What is preached instead is obedience – first and foremost, to the words of the priest, which, in turn, pushes any personal, inner spiritual life to the margins, if not outright shuns it. If anyone were to oppose this, they would be accused of disturbing the order in the church.

Motru's critique was directed at the broader phenomenon of institutional misalignment within Romanian society. Whether in the sphere of secular education, or religious practices, or that of economic or social life, we have sought topical solutions to systemic problems. And, as a result, we have failed to address the real issues leading to these deficiencies. What we can observe here is a tendency towards institutionalism and, most of all, a strong *étatisme*. The state was to be from that point on the main actor that ultimately defined the relationship between individuals and their ideal of authenticity. The form of organization of the state in particular, as an expression of society, he thought, corresponded in its principles to the spiritual attributes of the people who establish them. All this foreshadowed the political changes that were already beginning to take place, and those that were about to come, as well as the particularly active role that the state was to play in the economic, social and especially cultural life of the Romanians in the last years before the Second World War.

Ultimately, his assessment was not meant as a condemnation but as a diagnosis. He saw these traits not as immutable flaws but as characteristics shaped by historical and social circumstances. The challenge, then, was to cultivate the conditions in which the Romanian individual spirit could develop a more robust and autonomous sense of self, capable of resisting the ephemeral nature of foreign influences and grounding its identity in something deeper than volatile passions. A long overdue, and so far unresolved matter.

REFERENCES

- Blaga, L. (1937/2011). Geneza metaforei și sensul culturii. *Trilogia culturii*. Bucharest: Editura Humanitas, pp. 329-500.
- Comte, A. (1830–1842/1896). *The Positive Philosophy of Auguste Comte* (H. Martineau, Ed., Trans.), I. London: George Bell and Sons.
- Comte, A. (1851/1875). *System of Positive Polity, or Treatise on Sociology* (J.H. Bridges, Trans.), I. London: Longmans, Green and Co.
- Darwin, C. (1871/1981). *The Descent of Man, and Selection in Relation to Sex*, I. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

- Du Bois-Reymond, E. (1877/1912). Kulturgeschichte und Naturwissenschaft. *Reden von Emil du Bois-Reymond* (E. du Bois-Reymond, Ed.), I. Leipzig: Verlag von Veit and Comp., pp. 567–629.
- Gaukroger, S. (2020). Civilization and the Culture of Science: Science and the Shaping of Modernity, 1795–1935. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Herbart, J.F. (1816/1894). *A Text-Book in Psychology* (M. Smith, Trans.). New York: D. Appleton and Company.
- Hobbes, T. (1655/1839). Epistle Dedicatory. In Sir William Molesworth (Ed.), *The English Works of Thomas Hobbes*, I. London: John Bohn, Eminent Bookseller of Henrietta Street, Covent Garden, pp. vii–xii.
- Hobbes, T. (1656/1839). Elements of Philosophy. In Sir William Molesworth (Ed.), *The English Works of Thomas Hobbes*, I. London: John Bohn, Eminent Bookseller of Henrietta Street, Covent Garden.
- Kant, I. (1786/2004). *Metaphysical Foundations of Natural Science* (M. Friedman, Ed., Trans.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kant, I. (1787/2009). Preface to the Second Edition. In P. Guyer and A.W. Wood (Eds., Trans.), *The Critique of Pure Reason*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 106–124.
- Klautke, E. (2013). The Mind of the Nation: Völkerpsychologie in Germany 1851–1955. New York and Oxford: Berghahn.
- Kuper, A. (1973/2015). Anthropology and Anthropologists: The British School in the Twentieth Century. New York: Routledge.
- Leibniz, G.W. (1714/2014). The Monadology. In L. Strickland, *Leibniz's Monadology: A New Translation and Guide*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, pp. 14–33.
- Lupașcu, C.C. (2023). C. Rădulescu-Motru and the pursuit of a new science of the soul. *Studii de Istorie a Filosofiei Românești*, 19. Bucharest: Editura Academiei Române, pp. 56–75.
- Mamulea, M. (2021). Cercetarea experimentală a minții și limitele cunoașterii naturii: C. Rădulescu-Motru împotriva epifenomenalismului. *Studii de epistemologie și de teorie a valorilor*, 7. Bucharest: Editura Academiei Române, pp. 147–160.
- Radcliffe-Brown, A.R. (1949). Functionalism: A Protest. *American Anthropologist*, 51(2), pp. 320–323.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1897). Causalitatea mecanică și fenomenele psihice, I. *Convorbiri literare*, 27(1), pp. 41–57.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1904). *Cultura română și politicianismul*, Bucharest: Librăria Socecu and Co.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1908/1984). Puterea sufletească. *Personalismul energetic și alte scrieri*, (G. Al. Cazan, Ed.). Bucharest: Editura Eminescu, pp. 107–385.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1910). *Sufletul neamului nostru: calități bune și defecte*. Bucharest: Albert Baer.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1912). *Elemente de metafizică*. Bucharest: Societatea de Studii Filosofice din București.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1929a). *Curs de psihologie*. Bucharest: Editura Librăriei Socec and Co.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1929b). Cum trebuie înțeles naționalismul. *Dreptatea*, Year III, No. 3(442), p. 5.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1934–1935/1939). Nașterea spirituală a secolului nostru. *Românismul. Catehismul unei noi spiritualități*. Bucharest: Fundația pentru literatură și artă “Regele Carol II”, pp. 39–108.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1936/1939). *Românismul. Catehismul unei noi spiritualități*, Bucharest: Fundația pentru literatură și artă “Regele Carol II”.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1937). *Psihologia poporului român*. Bucharest: Societatea română de cercetări psihologice.
- Rădulescu-Motru, C. (1944/1996). *Revizuire și adăugiri*, II. Bucharest: Editura Floarea Darurilor.
- Schifirneț, C. (2003) *C. Rădulescu-Motru: Viața și faptele sale*, I. Bucharest: Editura Albatros.
- Schifirneț, C. (2004) *C. Rădulescu-Motru: Viața și faptele sale*, II. Bucharest: Editura Albatros.
- Spencer, H. (1864/1880). *The Principles of Biology*, I. London and Edinburgh: Williams and Norgate.
- Spengler, O. (1922/1926). Perspectives of World History. *The Decline of the West* (C.F. Atkinson, Trans.), II. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.

- Trencsényi, B. (2012) *The Politics of “National Character”: A Study in Interwar East European Thought*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Veit-Brause, I. (2001). Scientists and the cultural politics of academic disciplines in late 19th-century Germany: Emil Du Bois-Reymond and the controversy over the role of the cultural sciences. *History of the Human Sciences*, 14(4), pp. 31–56.
- Widerquist, K., and McCall G.S. (2017). The Hobbesian Hypothesis in Anthropology. *Prehistoric Myths in Modern Political Philosophy*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, pp. 112–131.
- Wundt, W. (1874/1903). *Grundzüge de physiologischen Psychologie*, III. Leipzig: Verlag von Wilhelm Engelmann.
- Xenopol, A.D. (1872). Resumat de prelegerile populare a Societății Junimea, anul al VIII-le. In prelegerea a șesa Domnul A. D. Xenopol vorbi despre naționalitate. *Convorbiri Literare*, 6(2), pp. 80–88.

